

Synchronous Primary Endometrial and Ovarian Cancers

Georgios Androutsopoulos* and Georgios Decavalas

Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Patras, Medical School, Rion 26500, Greece

Synchronous primary cancers are relatively uncommon in general population. About 0.5-1.7% of women with gynecological malignancies have synchronous primary cancers of the female genital tract [1-5]. Synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers are the most common combination [1,2,4].

The etiology and pathogenesis of synchronous primary cancers of the female genital tract, remains unclear [4,6]. The theory of the "secondary Müllerian system" has been proposed to explain the observation of multiple similar cancers in the female genital tract [6,7]. According to this theory, epithelia of the cervix, uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries and peritoneal surfaces simultaneously respond to a carcinogenic stimulus [6,7]. Shared hormonal receptors (estrogen receptors) may be responsible for the development of multiple primary malignancies in predisposed tissue [3,4,8].

It is also possible that synchronous presence of these cancers is an indicator of an etiologically distinct condition [9]. Perhaps patients have a more fragile genome and prior genetic damage may predispose to synchronous cancers [9-13]. Thus, embryologic, hormonal or other phenomena may be associated with the development of malignancies arising simultaneously in genital tissues [3,4,6-9,11].

Patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers had distinct clinical characteristics including: young age, obesity, premenopausal status and nulliparity [14]. Usually, they are 10 - 20 years younger than their counterparts with endometrial or ovarian cancer [2,15-17]. The median age at diagnosis is 50 years [1,14,16-19].

The most common presenting symptoms and signs are: abnormal uterine bleeding (46%), abdominal/pelvic pain (17%) and abdominal/pelvic mass (13%) [14,16,19,20].

Synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers may have a similar appearance or may be of different histologic types [4,15,18]. The distinction between metastatic and synchronous primary cancers is relatively easy, when they have different histologic types [21,22]. However, the distinction is relatively difficult when they share the same histologic features [21,22]. For that purpose in clinical practise we use well described empirical criteria [21,22].

For most patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers, systematic surgical staging is the baseline therapy [2,4,16-19,23-25]. Systematic surgical staging includes: total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, total omentectomy, appendectomy, pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy and complete resection of all disease [2,4,16-18,23-25]. Moreover, systematic surgical staging allows a more clear decision for stage related postoperative adjuvant therapy [24,25].

Especially in advanced stage patients, required a more aggressive management with postoperative adjuvant chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy [4,8,16,17,19,20,23,25,26]. The most active chemotherapeutic agents are: taxanes, anthracyclines and platinum compounds [16,19].

Prognostic factors for synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers are: age, stage of ovarian cancer, grade of endometrial cancer and adjuvant therapy [27]. Patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers endometrioid type have a better overall survival than patients with non-endometrioid or mixed

histologic subtypes [14]. Also, patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers have overall 5-year survival 85.9% and 10 year survival 80.3% [18].

The reason for better overall survival of patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers is not intuitively obvious [18]. Usually endometrial cancer produces early symptoms, so synchronous ovarian cancer may be detected at an earlier stage [4,10-13,20,23]. Moreover, favorable prognosis may be related with the detection of patients at early stage and low grade disease with an indolent growth rate [1,4,10-12-20-23].

References

1. Ayhan A, Yalçın OT, Tuncer ZS, Gürkan T, Küçükali T (1992) Synchronous primary malignancies of the female genital tract. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 45: 63-66.
2. Tong SY, Lee YS, Park JS, Bae SN, Lee JM, et al. (2008) Clinical analysis of synchronous primary neoplasms of the female reproductive tract. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 136: 78-82.
3. Deligdisch L, Szulman AE (1975) Multiple and multifocal carcinomas in female genital organs and breast. *Gynecol Oncol* 3: 181-190.
4. Eisner RF, Nieberg RK, Berek JS (1989) Synchronous primary neoplasms of the female reproductive tract. *Gynecol Oncol* 33: 335-339.
5. Matlock DL, Salem FA, Charles EH, Savage EW (1982) Synchronous multiple primary neoplasms of the upper female genital tract. *Gynecol Oncol* 13: 271-277.
6. Woodruff JD, Solomon D, Sullivant H (1985) Multifocal disease in the upper genital canal. *Obstet Gynecol* 65: 695-698.
7. Lauchlan SC (1972) The secondary Müllerian system. *Obstet Gynecol Surv* 27: 133-146.
8. Sica V, Nola E, Contieri E, Bova R, Masucci MT, et al. (1984) Estradiol and progesterone receptors in malignant gastrointestinal tumors. *Cancer Res* 44: 4670-4674.
9. Herrinton LJ, Voigt LF, Weiss NS, Beresford SA, Wingo PA (2001) Risk factors for synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers. *Ann Epidemiol* 11: 529-533.
10. Terzakis E, Androutsopoulos G, Grigoriadis C, Zygouris D, Derdelis G, et al. (2010) Synchronous primary endometrial and fallopian tube cancers. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 31: 467-468.
11. Androutsopoulos G, Adonakis G, Tsamantas A, Liosis S, Antonopoulos A, et al. (2008) Synchronous primary cancers in a woman with scleroderma: a case report. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 29: 548-550.
12. Decavalas G, Adonakis G, Androutsopoulos G, Gkgekos P, Koumoundourou D, et al. (2006) Synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers: a case report. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 27: 434-436.
13. Grigoriadis C, Androutsopoulos G, Zygouris D, Arnoyianni N, Terzakis

*Corresponding author: Georgios Androutsopoulos, Lecturer, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Patras, Medical School, Rion 26500, Greece, Tel: +306974088092; E-mail: androutsopoulos@upatras.gr

Received November 18, 2013; Accepted November 20, 2013; Published November 22, 2013

Citation: Androutsopoulos G, Decavalas G (2013) Synchronous Primary Endometrial and Ovarian Cancers. *J Community Med Health Educ* 3: e120. doi:10.4172/2161-0711.1000e120

Copyright: © 2013 Androutsopoulos G, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

- E (2012) Synchronous squamous cell carcinoma of the endometrium and endometrioid adenocarcinoma of the ovary. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 33: 666-668.
14. Soliman PT, Slomovitz BM, Broaddus RR, Sun CC, Oh JC, et al. (2004) Synchronous primary cancers of the endometrium and ovary: a single institution review of 84 cases. *Gynecol Oncol* 94: 456-462.
15. Pearl ML, Johnston CM, Frank TS, Roberts JA (1993) Synchronous dual primary ovarian and endometrial carcinomas. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 43: 305-312.
16. Liu Y, Li J, Jin H, Lu Y, Lu X (2013) Clinicopathological characteristics of patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers: A review of 43 cases. *Oncol Lett* 5: 267-270.
17. Signorelli M, Fruscio R, Lissoni AA, Pirovano C, Perego P, et al. (2008) Synchronous early-stage endometrial and ovarian cancer. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 102: 34-38.
18. Zaino R, Whitney C, Brady MF, DeGeest K, Burger RA, et al. (2001) Simultaneously detected endometrial and ovarian carcinomas—a prospective clinicopathologic study of 74 cases: a gynecologic oncology group study. *Gynecol Oncol* 83: 355-362.
19. Chiang YC, Chen CA, Huang CY, Hsieh CY, Cheng WF (2008) Synchronous primary cancers of the endometrium and ovary. *Int J Gynecol Cancer* 18: 159-164.
20. Sheu BC, Lin HH, Chen CK, Chao KH, Shun CT, et al. (1995) Synchronous primary carcinomas of the endometrium and ovary. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 51: 141-146.
21. Ulbright TM, Roth LM (1985) Metastatic and independent cancers of the endometrium and ovary: a clinicopathologic study of 34 cases. *Hum Pathol* 16: 28-34.
22. Scully R, Young R, Clement P (1998) Tumors of the ovary, maldeveloped gonads, fallopian tube, and broad ligament. In: Armed Forces Institute of Pathology/American Registry of Pathology WD, editor. *Atlas of Tumor Pathology*.
23. Androutsopoulos G, Adonakis G, Tsamandas A, Andonopoulos A, Decavalas G (2011) Systemic Sclerosis and Multiple Cancers of the Female Genital Tract: Prolonged Survival following Current Treatment Strategies. *Case Rep Rheumatol* 2011: 392068.
24. Androutsopoulos G (2012) Current Treatment Options in Patients with Endometrial Cancer. *J Community Med Health Educ* 2: e113.
25. Androutsopoulos G, Decavalas G (2013) Management of endometrial cancer. *International Journal of Translation & Community Medicine* 1: e101.
26. Eifel P, Hendrickson M, Ross J, Ballon S, Martinez A, et al. (1982) Simultaneous presentation of carcinoma involving the ovary and the uterine corpus. *Cancer* 50: 163-170.
27. Ayhan A, Guvenal T, Coskun F, Basaran M, Salman MC (2003) Survival and prognostic factors in patients with synchronous ovarian and endometrial cancers and endometrial cancers metastatic to the ovaries. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 24: 171-174.

Citation: Androutsopoulos G, Decavalas G (2013) Synchronous Primary Endometrial and Ovarian Cancers. *J Community Med Health Educ* 3: e120. doi:10.4172/2161-0711.1000e120

Submit your next manuscript and get advantages of OMICS Group submissions

Unique features:

- User friendly/feasible website-translation of your paper to 50 world's leading languages
- Audio Version of published paper
- Digital articles to share and explore

Special features:

- 300 Open Access Journals
- 25,000 editorial team
- 21 days rapid review process
- Quality and quick editorial, review and publication processing
- Indexing at PubMed (partial), Scopus, EBSCO, Index Copernicus and Google Scholar etc
- Sharing Option: Social Networking Enabled
- Authors, Reviewers and Editors rewarded with online Scientific Credits
- Better discount for your subsequent articles

Submit your manuscript at: <http://www.omicsonline.org/submission/>